

I.FAST

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

First characterisation of beam windows materials under thermomechanical load and extended radiation damage

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ABSTRACT

MS13 reports the activity carried out by WP4 in the frame of the material selection and characterization for applications in beam windows manufacturing.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	M.Losasso, M.Tomut		14/12/2022
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	CERN	16/12/2022
Approved by	Steering Committee		16/12/2022

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This MS13 reports on the activity made at CERN and GSI to identify, select, procure, and characterise materials able to be adopted in the manufacturing of the beam windows for accelerators.

1 Introduction

Beam windows are essential components of accelerators and experimental systems. They are subjected to extreme level of radiation, temperature, thermal stresses, dynamic pressure, and stresses conditions. The materials employed must present the proper mechanical properties necessary for interacting directly with the beam while keeping the necessary mechanical stability.

To develop windows able to sustain the high intensity beams of next generation accelerators, the WP4 is tasked to identify the best available materials and to characterize samples of these materials in a representative radiation environment.

1.1 MATERIALS IDENTIFICATION AND SELECTION

The proper materials must be able at the same time to sustain the pressure differences between the vacuum side of the beam and the external environment, the thermal pulse and energy deposition of the beam, and the radiation damage. This requires leak-tight materials with high mechanical strength, low thermal expansion, low atomic number to better resist the radiation and be more “transparent” to the beam avoiding scattering effects.

At first we have focused on the materials that have been so far used in this context worldwide in the accelerators. In literature these were identified to be: Berillium, Titanium Alloys, Nickel superalloys, Stainless Steel, Aluminium Alloys. More in details:

- Titanium Grade 5 (Ti-6Al-4V) exhibits high strength and excellent fatigue performance, it is a titanium alloy utilized in several CERN and FermiLab beam lines and in J-PARC neutrino facility, recently has been planned to be adopted as target containment window in in the future Long Baseline Neutrino Facility at Fermilab and as target of new PIP-II accelerator for the international Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment;
- 6061-T6 aluminium alloy, exhibits high corrosion resistance and high strength to resist the heating effects of beam energy deposition, planned to be utilized as baseline material of the 5W-Proton Beam Window at European Spallation Source (ESS);
- T91 steel (9Cr-1Mo), a ferritic/martensitic steel with strong corrosion resistance, good creep rupture strength and low coefficient of thermal expansion, selected for the realization of the ADS beam windows and tested in the Megawatt pilot experiment (MEGAPIE);
- Graphenic carbon, for its extremely high thermal conductivity, high intrinsic strength and high transparency to high-energy ions, and other promising ultra-thin materials, such as Silicon Nitride (Si₃N₄), Silicon Carbide (SiC).

Some of these materials, could have been already widely characterized, however, there is still an interest to perform a comparative analysis based on uniform conditions. Based on the above, we have started to procure the materials necessary to be successively machined and irradiated. Needless to say, buying the small quantity necessary of these metals would have been mission impossible both for the time involved (we needed to fit the beam time of GSI) and for the cost. We were helped in this challenge by our industrial partner (RHP) who made available the samples, in the right shape and dimension to fit the GSI sample-holder.

1.2 SIMULATION AND BENCHMARK

In parallel with the activity in GSI, at CERN, Lorenzo Notari has reproduced the geometry of the samples in a ANSYS model, as reported in Fig. 1. With ANSYS has been simulated the phases of heat propagation, following the energy deposition, as well as the thermal response of the beam interaction with the window and its dynamic behaviour. All these parameters were expected to be measured during the measuring campaign in GSI. Indeed in Fig.2, Fig.3 and Fig.4 are reported the main simulated and measured relevant parameters.

Fig 1: sample holder and ANSYS model

Fig 2: beam induced heating

Fig 3: phases of heat propagation

Fig 4: analysis of vibration

Another analysis that has been carried out has involved the investigation on damage induced by radiation. The common unit of measure of damage is the displacement per atom, dpa. One dpa is the dose at which, on average, each atom in the material has been displaced once. Required lifetimes of the most highly irradiated components in accelerators systems such as the targets and beam windows are expected to be in the range of tens of dpa.

For this analysis a SRIM code has been used to simulate the particle transport in the material of the windows.

Fig 5: Particle transport simulation

1.3 IRRADIATION CAMPAIGN

For the allocated beam time in March 2022 at GSI, a test campaign has involved the four materials: T91, Ti grade 23, Inconel 718, Al 6082 T6, in thickness from 0.22 μm , to 0.4 μm . The samples were machined and installed on appropriate sample holders to be mounted inside the Spectroscopy chamber of the beamline, to be exposed to a U-ion flux as long as necessary to accumulate a fluence of 2.0×10^{13} ions/cm².

Figure 6 shows the samples in their respective sample-holder before and after irradiations.

Fig 6: Particle transport simulation

A Thermal Camera was used to control the beam-induced heating of the samples and a Laser Doppler Vibrometer (LDV) was used to record the surface velocity signal of the samples. In Fig.7 is shown the experimental arrangement and in Fig.8 and Fig 9 are reported some of the experimental results.

Laser Doppler Vibrometer

Fig 7: Experimental arrangement

Fig 8: Experimental Results. Laser Doppler Vibrometer

Fig 9: Experimental results. Thermal camera

2 Conclusions and future plans

The experimental investigations and the numerical benchmark have succeeded in the original aim of understanding the thermal diffusion phenomena for quasi-instantaneous heat deposition. We have realized that the sample-holder and the fixing arrangement in the irradiation facility is critical in order to reach high accuracy in the measurement. Next irradiation experiments must provide for a more refined procedure for mounting the test specimens to reduce the influence of the boundary conditions.

The use of LDV systems able to capture frequencies of the order of the MHz are suggested for catching the frequencies of propagating waves, more appropriate to assess local damages and less sensitive to edge conditions

Eventually, other promising materials for beam windows, including graphitic materials and graphene, will be proposed for test in the next irradiation experiments. These depends on the availability of the beam in GSI, which is now not yet defined.